

An Efficient Utilization of mm-Wave and THz-Wave for V2X Communication

Author: Sameer Kumar Singh, Rohit Singh, Brijesh Kumbhani,
Sam Darshi, Satyam Agarwal
Presented By: Sameer Kumar Singh

IIT ROPAR, Electrical Engineering Department
Rupnagar, Punjab
INDIA

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Outline

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Key Aspect of mm-wave and THz wave
- 3 System Model
- 4 Challenges and Open Problems
- 5 Conclusion and Future Scope

Introduction: Use-Cases of Vehicular Communication

- Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I)
- Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V)
- Vehicle to Pedestrian (V2P)
- Vehicle to Everything (V2X)

Key Aspect of mm-Wave

- Large bandwidth (24-100 GHz Band)
- High data rate
- Higher susceptibility to blockages
- Shorter wavelength and smaller Antenna
- Support MIMO and low interference

Key Aspect of THz-Wave

- Enormous bandwidth (0.1-10 THz band)
- Short range communication
- High directivity
- High beam-forming gain
- Limited interference

System Model

Figure: An illustration of proposed architecture

- Introduces a novel approach to integrate various frequency bands (i.e., microwave, mm-wave, and THz-wave)
- There we consider two distinct traffic scenarios:
 - (i) *Transmission Schemes for V2I Communication*
 - (ii) *Transmission Schemes for V2V Communication*

(i) Transmission Schemes for V2I Communication

- In V2I, we establish a direct link between vehicles and RSU,
- We employ a hybrid link (integration of microwave and mm-wave) , which increase network coverage.
- In general, the received SINR (at CV-k from RSU-i):

$$SINR_{k,i} = \frac{S_{k,i}}{I_k + \sigma^2} \quad (1)$$

- So, achievable rate of the V2I scenario as:

$$R_{k,i} = \log_2(1 + SINR_{k,i}) \quad (2)$$

(ii) *Transmission Schemes for V2V Communication*

- In V2V, vehicles exchange real-time information, such as speed, position, and status, with nearby vehicles.
- For this, we mounted a transceiver or antenna of THz frequencies on the running vehicles for the information exchange.
- The advantage of using THz for V2V is that the path loss at this high frequency is huge. Thus, the interference to the far off vehicles is minimal.
- In general, the received SINR (at CV-j from CV-i)

$$SINR_{j,i} = \frac{S_{j,i}}{I_j + \phi_j + \sigma^2} \quad (3)$$

Challenges and Open Problems

- The main challenge with the integration of various frequency bands comes from the path loss resulting in different attenuation.
- Large overheads, High computational cost.
- Required advanced beam tracking techniques.

Conclusion and Future Scope

- This paper presents the integration of higher frequency bands with the conventional frequency band to improve the performance of moving vehicles.
- Furthermore, this study opens numerous opportunities for future research, including hand-off minimization, and latency optimization.

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Thank You